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Articulating Dayak Indigeneity through Gendered Media, Youth Activism, and Global Connectivities

Edwin Jurriëns | ORCID: 0000-0003-4207-4529

University of Melbourne, Melbourne, Australia

edwin.jurriens@unimelb.edu.au

Aryo Danusiri | ORCID: 0000-0003-1097-9884

University of Indonesia, Jakarta, Indonesia

aryo.danusiri@ui.ac.id

A. Rugun Sirait | ORCID: 0009-0002-5356-8815

University of Vienna, Vienna, Austria

amelia.rugun.sirait@univie.ac.at

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Abstract

This article focuses on the Ranu Welum foundation based in Palangka Raya, Central Kalimantan, an independent youth and media initiative that actively studies and reshapes notions of 'Dayakness'. The foundation seeks to connect with global networks of Indigenous communities and address its environmental, socio-political, and health concerns in the international domain. We pay special attention to the short documentaries directed or produced by its founder, Emmanuela Shinta. We discuss how her films represent and contribute to the foundation's expansion of networks, gendered perspectives on social and environmental struggles, and intertwining of the voices of activists, Indigenous communities, and nature. This article seeks to bring new insights to studies of Indigenous media use and female documentary-making in Indonesia, by analysing the paradoxical interconnections between the expression of local concerns and communal identity on the one hand and the global media use and individual self-imaging of local youth on the other.

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Keywords

indigeneity – documentary – youth activism – Dayak identity – gender – environmentalism – Central Kalimantan – Indonesia

1 Introduction

Social theories have historically examined issues of identity, representation, and authority, making them effective instruments for scrutinizing the portrayal and setting of Indigenous peoples in media. These theories provide frameworks for comprehending the historical, cultural, and political settings which impact Indigenous identities and their representations in media.¹ Postcolonial and critical race theorists have emphasized the media's role in perpetuating colonial and racial inequalities, whilst Indigenous Studies scholars stress the significance of self-representation and epistemic sovereignty in contesting mainstream narratives (Simpson 2017; Wilson 2008).

This article analyses how Dayak youth from Central Kalimantan, Indonesia, use digital media and in-person activities for environmental activism and exploring and shaping their own and their community's identity as 'Indigenous'. It focuses on the Ranu Welum foundation (est. 2016) based in Palangka Raya, Central Kalimantan, an independent youth and media initiative that actively studies and reshapes notions of 'Dayakness'. The foundation seeks to connect with global networks of Indigenous communities and address its environmental, socio-political, and health concerns in the international domain. This article addresses how and why it does this, with a special focus on the creative use of visual and textual media, especially documentary film, by its young, predominantly female, activist leaders. We argue that their articulation of Indigeneity encompasses complex mediations between the personal and the political, the individual and the communal, the private and the public, lived experiences and discursive representations, emotions and tactics, the online and the offline, and the human and the natural.

We demonstrate that the articulation of Indigeneity is a dynamic, ongoing process, which has drawn the interest of a younger generation using digital media to carve a position for themselves and their community in the world. We follow Tania Li's (2000:151) argument that 'a group's self-identification as tribal or indigenous is not natural or inevitable, but neither is it simply invented,

1 Hall 1997; Said 1978; Smith 1999; Spivak 1988.

adopted, or imposed'. Similar to other activist initiatives, Ranu Welum relies on, mainly young and female, 'cultural brokers' (Bräuchler 2019), who engage with a large variety of digital and in-person platforms to constantly rediscover and reinvent notions of Dayakness in the face of never-ending and always-changing global, national, and local environmental, socio-political, and cultural challenges. While building on and expanding the emerging field of studies of contemporary Indigenous media and art activism with time- and place-specific examples of cultural brokerage, this article counters findings from earlier times and other places that suggest irreconcilable tensions between collective (re)production and individual expression and creative experimentation (Ginsburg 1994). Instead, Ranu Welum's female leadership's digital creativity, including engagement with social media trends and selfie styles, is meant to present their personal bodies, voices, and stories for the greater good of the broader Dayak community.

We first discuss Ranu Welum's use of English and international discourses around Indigeneity to present Dayakness to the world and connect with global audiences, including other Indigenous groups. Then we analyse the interconnections between its online and offline activities, including the knowledge-sharing and firefighting, reforestation, and other action programmes of its so-called Youth Act Kalimantan initiative. In the following sections, we focus on the lived experiences, activism, media production, discourses, and aesthetics of its female leaders in their roles as cultural brokers between the private and public, and the local and global. We pay special attention to the short documentaries directed and/or produced by Ranu Welum founder and CEO Emmanuela Shinta. We examine how her films represent and contribute to the foundation's expansion of networks, gendered perspectives on social and environmental struggles, and intertwining of the voices of activists, Indigenous communities, and nature.

This article seeks to bring new insights to studies of Indigenous media use and female documentary-making in Indonesia, by analysing the, arguably paradoxical, interconnections between the expression of local concerns and communal identity on the one hand and the global media use and individual self-imaging of local youth on the other. We came into contact with Ranu Welum via 'Fire Play: Understanding and Documenting Indigenous Fire Governance in Indonesia', a 2023–2024 collaborative research project of the Anthropology Studies Unit of the Lembaga Penelitian dan Pengembangan Sosial dan Politik (Institute for Social and Political Research and Development, LPPSP) at Universitas Indonesia, Jakarta; the Asia Institute at the University of Melbourne; the Badan Riset dan Inovasi Nasional (National Research and Innovation Agency, BRIN), Indonesia; and the Yayasan Puter Indonesia (Puter Indone-

sia Foundation). The article is based on the discursive analysis of Ranu Welum's website and personal communication, fieldwork meetings, and a workshop with its members, especially with its current managing director and former coordinator of youth and community programmes, Sarasi Sylvester Sinurat. The analysed documentaries were selected based on their popularity, topicality, and/or comprehensiveness. The analysis of their content, style, production, distribution, and socio-political contexts is meant to demonstrate the unique, challenging, and real-life dynamics of what it means to become, rather than be, Indigenous in the twenty-first century (Clifford 2013).

2 Indigeneity in Contemporary Indonesia

Ranu Welum is a product of the enhanced access to digital media and the increased freedom of expression since Reformasi, the Indonesian democratic reform since the fall of President Soeharto's authoritarian New Order regime (1967–1998). It is an example of Southeast Asian youth combining social and other media and in-person activities for socio-political causes, going well beyond 'slacktivism', or 'a less meaningful activism driven by self-presentation, group identification and narcissistic motivations that may even hinder broader social-political activism efforts' (Halimatusa'diyah 2024:2). It has also been shaped by one of the other defining features of Reformasi, namely the government efforts at decentralizing administrative and economic power from the capital, Jakarta, to the regions, and supporting certain degrees of *otonomi daerah* or regional autonomy. One aspect of this dynamic has been local communities advocating self-governance based on *adat* or customary laws and practices (Tyson 2010:10). In March 1999, the first nationwide network of *adat* communities, called Aliansi Masyarakat Adat Nusantara (AMAN, Archipelagic Alliance of Adat Communities), was formed during a congress in which they famously declared: 'if the state will not acknowledge us, then we will not acknowledge the state' (Henley and Davidson 2007:1). While AMAN has received considerable political and academic attention, less studied, more informal or smaller-scale initiatives like Ranu Welum point to the importance of also acknowledging and analysing the role of young people and popular media in articulating Indigeneity.

Historically, and even today, Indigenous identity is not commonly expressed or accepted in Indonesia. The official state discourse of the New Order denied Indigeneity, by alternating between claims that Indonesia did not have any Indigenous groups, or that all Indonesians were equally Indigenous (Li 2000: 149). Rural groups in the so-called 'outer' islands of the Indonesian archipelago,

including Kalimantan and West Papua, were designated as *masyarakat terasing* (estranged communities) or *masyarakat terpencil* (isolated communities) in need of government-led agricultural and other economic development projects (Li 2000:154). The government introduced a uniform administration system with state-endorsed regional and village bureaucracies replacing traditional leaders and institutions of local governance (Henley and Davidson 2007:10). The media and cultural sectors were admonished to refrain from critical engagement with purportedly divisive issues related to *suku* (tribe, ethnic group), *agama* (religion), *ras* (race), and *antar golongan* (inter-group relations, including those between social classes and ideology-based groups), collectively abbreviated to the acronym SARA (Sen and Hill 2000:12). Instead, the national motto of *Bhinneka Tunggal Ika* (Unity in Diversity) was to be supported by uniform, depoliticized representations of cultural and ethnic diversity (Bräuchler 2019:6; Henley and Davidson 2007:10). One of the missions of Ranu Welum is precisely to present divergent, re-politicized manifestations of Dayakness.

Part of the state development agenda was the introduction of transmigration programmes that over the course of the New Order relocated more than five million farmers and other workers from predominantly poorer and overpopulated parts of Java and Bali to marginalized regions, including Ranu Welum's homeland, Central Kalimantan (Henley and Davidson 2007:10). The Undang-Undang Pokok Agraria (Basic Agrarian Law) 1960 formalized state rights and private ownership over land that used to be governed by vernacular and customary forms of tenure (McCarthy and Robinson 2016:112). Moreover, the Departemen Kehutanan (Ministry of Forestry) during the New Order classified forest areas that were subject to local customary laws as 'free state domain' (McCarthy and Robinson 2016:12). Land concessions and development licenses were allocated to timber, mining, oil, gas, and palm oil businesses close to government (McCarthy and Robinson 2016:12).

An important trigger for the *adat* movement since the late 1990s has been communities demanding a return of, or fair compensation for, ancestral lands that had been claimed by the government for state development projects (Henley and Davidson 2007:13). Central to *adat* are historical practices, rules, and rights regarding the control of land that are outside modern state laws (Henley and Davidson 2007:3). Some of the *adat* conventions around customary land rights were shaped and codified by Dutch scholarship during colonial times (Tyson 2010:7; Hauser-Schäublin 2013:10; Henley and Davidson 2007:22). David Henley and Jamie Davidson (2007:3–4) argue that Indonesian *adat* communities tend to focus on the intersections between history, land, and law rather than the recurring themes of identity and cultural and linguistic distinctiveness in international campaigns on Indigeneity. The youth involved in Ranu Welum,

on the other hand, actively explore and change concepts and practices of Indigeneity, by engaging with communities dealing with similar issues in Indonesia and globally.

3 The Ranu Welum Foundation: Presenting Dayakness to the World

In both the international and Indonesian discourses, a defining feature of Indigeneity is the self-identification of communities as Indigenous or customary. In addition to self-ascription, other common criteria to designate communities as Indigenous are 'first-come' (as descendants from first inhabitants), 'non-dominant' (as citizens under the alien structure of the modern state), and 'culturally different' (as minorities) (Martinez Cobo 1982; Tyson 2010:5). In international meetings and on the English-language version of its website, AMAN presents itself as 'the Indigenous Peoples' Alliance of the Archipelago'.² The reference to 'Indigenous' rather than 'customary' in the English translation facilitates strategic linkages with Indigenous movements around the world (Hauser-Schäublin 2013:10). At the same time, its use is limited to the translation, subdued to the use of *adat* in the original name of the organization, thus indicating meaningful differences between the two concepts (Li 2000:155).

Other organizations may exclusively use one of the two concepts; interchange indistinctively between the two; or acknowledge their differences, while prioritizing one of them. Ranu Welum falls into the last category, by outlining aspects of both concepts but predominantly using English in its statements and engaging more fully with the international discourse on Indigeneity. The textual and visual discourses of Dayak Indigeneity in its films, social media, and educational and activist programmes are specific forms of agency rooted in, and responding to, complex and fluid intersections of historical and contemporary social, political, and cultural dynamics at the local, national, and international levels. Following Tania Li (2000:151), the discourses are part of the process of articulating the group's self-positioning as Indigenous at a certain socio-political conjuncture:

[...] a positioning which draws upon historically sedimented practices, landscapes, and repertoires of meaning, and emerges through particular patterns of engagement and struggle. The conjunctures at which (some) people come to identify themselves as indigenous, realigning the ways

² <https://www.aman.or.id/> (accessed 5-8-2025).

they connect to the nation, the government, and their own, unique tribal place, are the contingent products of agency and the cultural and political work of articulation.

Ranu Welum, established in 2016, emerged at the juncture of multiple socio-political flows and developments since the late 1990s, including, but not limited to, the increased freedom of expression in the post-New Order period of democratic reform; the media savviness of a generation that has grown up with digital media and the internet; the growth of international communication and creative networks; the enhanced presence of *adat* communities; and the leadership of female cultural activists.

The foundation is an activist response to the destruction of forests, water and air pollution, and confiscation of lands by logging, coal and gold mining, and palm oil companies in Central Kalimantan. One of its taglines underlining its activism is: ‘The world will not be destroyed by those who do evil, but by those who watch them without doing anything.’³ It researches and undertakes practical actions against the negative impact of environmental destruction on people’s health, economic conditions, social structures, cultural identities, and freedoms and rights. This is reflected in its name, *ranu welum*, which means ‘the water of life’ in the language of Dayak Maanyan, a predominantly Christian ethnic group from the provinces of Central and South Kalimantan.⁴ The name underlines that the foundation approaches the conservation of the environment not in isolation but by intersecting it with the preservation of culture and the struggle for Indigenous rights.⁵

On its website, the foundation presents itself as ‘a Dayak youth initiative that combines indigenous knowledge and modern technology to empower indigenous youth to preserve the culture, protect the forest and fight for the indigenous rights.’⁶ It is run by young people, predominantly but not exclusively of a Dayak ethnic background, and has women in key positions. It also relies on donations and support from various international partner organizations,⁷ including Big Red Button,⁸ Rainforest 4 Foundation,⁹ Tri Upcycle,¹⁰ Eyes of the World Films,¹¹

3 <http://www.ranuwelum.org/our-story/> (accessed 5-8-2025).

4 <https://ifnotusthenwho.me/who/ranu-welum-foundation/> (accessed 5-8-2025).

5 Sinurat, personal communication, 16-11-2023.

6 <http://www.ranuwelum.org/our-story/> (accessed 5-8-2025).

7 <http://www.ranuwelum.org/ranu-welums-friends> (accessed 5-8-2025).

8 <http://bigredbutton.com.sg/#about> (accessed 5-8-2025).

9 <https://www.rainforest4.org/> (accessed 5-8-2025).

10 <https://tricycle.co.id/> (accessed 5-8-2025).

11 <https://www.eyesoftheworldfilms.com/> (accessed 5-8-2025).

and David Metcalf Photography.¹² Its mission statement identifies Indigenous digital storytelling and social media as tools for ‘decolonizing’ the environment and the Dayak community from the impact of contemporary forms of resource colonialism.¹³ The references to both Indigeneity and decolonizing are ways of rephrasing and reinterpreting local concerns, establishing connections with an international network of Indigenous communities, and creating new forms of visibility and affirmation from youthful and gendered perspectives that may or may not be in line with the perspectives of male *adat* elders. They reflect the desire of the Dayak and other youth to express Indigeneity not only in local terms but also in connection with broader, topical and cosmopolitan debates and discourses around human rights and environmental sustainability.

The online description of one of Ranu Welum’s documentaries, tellingly titled *Dayak: Facing the giants* (2019), published on YouTube on 26 November 2019,¹⁴ provides a strong activist statement about the links between colonization and the destruction of the environment, public health, and Indigenous rights and identities:

The giants of modern colonization have been killing the indigenous community slowly. It’s in the form of massive industries that caused devastating environmental destruction and social conflicts. It’s also in the form of mega forest fires that suffocate us with toxic smoke haze. But it is not too late. You and I have to act. Now. No matter how big the giants are.

The start of the documentary puts the struggle of the Dayak people in a global context by showing footage of internationally known Greta Thurnberg and other young, female activists in a Climate Strike event. It also shows part of a conference speech about the threats of climate change by UN Secretary-General Antonio Guterres.

The film follows Ranu Welum activist Marsela Arnanda on her journey to research the impact of deforestation in Talekoi, one of the oldest villages in the South Baretu regency in Central Kalimantan and the homeland of the family of Ranu Welum’s founder Emmanuela Shinta (Shinta 2018:12). Arnanda meets with female Dayak Maanyan elder Talina and fisherman Amran, who explain that erosion only started with the logging activities of the PT Sindo Lumber company. The Nanyu river between the Talekoi and Bundar villages used to

12 <https://www.davidmetcalfphotography.com/> (accessed 5-8-2025).

13 <http://www.ranuwelum.org/our-missions/> (accessed 5-8-2025).

14 <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=lahXntHAYwg> (accessed 5-8-2025).

be deep enough for fishing, but today it is so shallow that people can cross it by foot. Villagers have been jobless, have lost other livelihoods such as rubber tapping, or have been forced into unstable or low-paying occupations such as gold mining. One of the other villagers explains that logging and mining companies such as PT Palopo Indah initially promised to give jobs to the villagers whose lands had been confiscated but instead have been hiring workers from outside.

One of the other protagonists in the documentary is anthropologist Dr Marko Mahin, who argues that the agricultural knowledge and practices of the Dayak people are not the source but the solution to the current environmental and health problems. He explains that the Dayak people do not see themselves as superior to nature but try to maintain harmonious relationships with the environment. They are not led by greed and only take from the forests, soils, and waterways what is necessary to survive, while leaving intact sufficient resources for future generations. In short, the documentary demonstrates Ranu Welum's international interconnectedness, its politicization and contextualization of local environmental problems, and its thinking about sustainable solutions by taking into account local Dayak wisdom and cultural and agricultural traditions.

With its discourses, media productions, and participation in international conventions, Ranu Welum stands out as an Indonesian cultural organization that uses the notion of 'Indigenous' in English to frame social and environmental issues and convey its messages to a worldwide audience. According to its current managing director, Sarasi Sylvester Sinurat, who has a Batak ethnic background and is from North Sumatra, this is necessary, considering the global causes and impact of the environmental problems the Dayak communities are dealing with: '[T]ogether we try how we can be heard outside, be heard globally. If we only solve the issues in Indonesia, they won't be solved.'¹⁵ In Ranu Welum's publications, the international discourses are prominent but do not exclude more common references to Indigeneity in Indonesian such as *masyarakat adat* (customary law community). Moreover, Indigeneity is interconnected with other forms of agency and identity, including youth action, female leadership, and human–nature relationships. In other words, the foundation seeks to make the notion of Dayakness relatable to broader Indonesian society and the world through its own, contemporary articulations of Indigeneity.

15 Sarasi Sylvester Sinurat, personal communication, 16-11-2023.

4 Creative Media and Youth Activism for Indigenous and Environmental Struggles

Ranu Welum utilizes textual and visual discourses, action programmes, and networking to sustain its struggle and make the Dayak plight known to others. It pays special attention to digital film, video, and social media as tools of information and communication, storytelling, intergenerational knowledge exchange, and activism. Its media productions highlight female agency and communal values in tackling environmental, social, and/or personal issues. Ranu Welum gives a voice to minorities that are underrepresented in the Indonesian mainstream media and broader socio-political realm, in which majority perspectives—adult, male, Javanese, and/or Islamic—prevail.

The foundation has produced its own films, videos, websites, blogs, and social media posts, and has also provided media training to youth and other groups in society. According to its website, '[t]he access to digital information and media training that Ranu Welum provides gives Dayak youth a platform to advocate for indigenous rights, especially land rights; we give voice to forest protection while also building a better future in communities in terms of education, economies, and culture preservation'.¹⁶ Since 2018, it has also organized an annual International Indigenous Film Festival (IIFFF) in four different locations: Palangka Raya (Central Kalimantan), Ubud (Bali, in collaboration with New Zealand photographer David Metcalf), Kuching (Malaysia), and Bhubaneswar (India).¹⁷

Sinurat mentioned, however, that the foundation has been criticized by some locals 'for only talking via social media' without demonstrating 'what their [real] actions are for helping *adat* communities'.¹⁸ We argue that this criticism underestimates the informational, critical, and performative action values of textual and visual discourses. Moreover, it ignores the Indigenous background of its members, and the close interconnection between Ranu Welum's online and offline activities, including its multiple educational and disaster relief campaigns. It may reflect a lack of familiarity with the media, interests, and discourses of the young people by outsiders or members of the older Dayak generation.

The foundation itself divides its in-person activities into two different categories: knowledge programmes and action programmes. Its knowledge pro-

16 <http://www.ranuwelum.org/our-story/> (accessed 5-8-2025).

17 <http://www.ranuwelum.org/academy> (accessed 5-8-2025).

18 Sinurat, personal communication, 16-11-2023.

grammes include the Ranu Welum Film Academy for film production and digital storytelling; the Sekolah Adat (customary school) Anri Arai Atei for children's education about local culture and wisdom; a children's library; and the publication of an e-book, titled *Indigenous digital storytelling: How to make your own media training* (2022).¹⁹ Young Dayak people are also helped with starting up their own business by Ranu Welum's co-founder and current executive director, Roro Ardy Garini. They can learn from Garini's experiences as a social entrepreneur in clothing and culinary businesses.²⁰

Ranu Welum's action-oriented programmes include the Youth Act Kalimantan for recruiting youth in climate action and climate justice projects. It also encompasses The Heartland Project for reforestation and eco-restoration in Kalimantan through tree-planting, ironwood conservation, the promotion of agroforestry, and the formation of forest rangers teams. With another programme, Kalimantan Relief Effort, the foundation provided support in the wake of disasters such as the 2015 forest fires and haze, and the 2021 floods and landslides. The support included the provision of volunteer fire fighters, haze shelters, N95 masks, food, clothes, and medical help. One of its radical efforts to reforest and restore the ecology has been the purchase of a 6-ha teak forest in Tangkiling, Palangka Raya. It has been designated as the site of Ranu Welum's new Youth Act Kalimantan ecology centre for environmental research, learning, and camping.²¹ These are all examples of the tangible impact of the foundation.

Ranu Welum has also initiated various demonstrations and petitions, including the 2019 Kalimantan Climate Strike petition²² against soil and forest fires. This petition, directed to then Indonesian President Joko Widodo (2014–2024), the governors of Kalimantan, and Minister of Environment and Forestry Siti Nurbaya Bakar, demanded: 1) action against corporations that are responsible for environmental destruction; 2) the protection of education and health by providing smoke-free shelters at schools; and 3) an end to scapegoating local farmers for the fires. During the 2023 Climate Strike, Ranu Welum and its collaborators expressed their hopes and demands for the 2024 presidential and parliamentary elections. These included fair elections, free from the interference by oligarchs; political commitment to tackling climate change, including the transition to renewable energy sources; and rejection of the funding of

19 <http://www.ranuwelum.org/academy> (accessed 5-8-2025).

20 <https://ifnotusthenwho.me/who/ro-ro-ardya-garini/> (accessed 5-8-2025).

21 <http://www.ranuwelum.org/conservation> (accessed 5-8-2025).

22 <http://www.ranuwelum.org/community> (accessed 5-8-2025).

election campaigns by coal and other fossil fuel industries.²³ Obviously, these aspirations received a major setback with the election of Prabowo Subianto as Indonesia's new president. Like his predecessor Joko Widodo, Prabowo is part of long-established oligarchic networks with business interests in environmentally destructive industries and development projects.

5 Articulating Indigeneity through Cultural Brokerage

Ranu Welum's strategic engagement with digital media follows a trend of Indigenous communities, activists, and scholars using or analysing independent media production and distribution for articulating Indigeneity and interconnecting Indigenous groups from different parts of the globe. The history of the annual international Indigenous film and video event Dreamspeakers Festival in Edmonton, Canada, goes back as far as 1992. Festivals like this promote not only Indigenous media production and joint production, but also Indigenous festival management and the distribution and exchange of films and videos among Indigenous communities (Ginsburg 1994:377). Based on her research of this festival as well as Australian Aboriginal video, film, and television production since the late 1970s, Faye Ginsburg (1994:377) argued that Indigenous visual media should not be approached as textual objects of individual freedom and self-expression but as dynamic arenas of cultural production and social interaction. She observed that 'indigenous producers reject this dominant model of the media text as the expression of an individuated self and continue to stress their work as on a continuum of social action authorizing Aboriginal cultural empowerment' (Ginsburg 1994:378).

The media activities and concerns of Ranu Welum anno 2024, on the other hand, seem to combine both individuality and communality. Its collective (re)production does not exclude, but to a considerable extent integrates and relies on, personal expression and creative experimentation. In that sense, it does not contradict but embraces Ginsburg's (1994:368) notion of 'embedded aesthetics', or 'a system of evaluation that refuses a separation of textual production and circulation from broader arenas of social relations'. Being run by young activists who are well versed in social media use, digital creativity, and selfie culture, it presents the bodies, voices, and personal stories of young, female protagonists and other charismatic leaders and members of Dayak com-

23 Sinurat, personal communication, 16-11-2023.

munities in short documentaries and social media posts to convey its environmental and social concerns to the world. It shapes its own forms of Indigeneity through networking and collaborating with other Indigenous groups from Indonesia and elsewhere, while also seeking to reach broader international audiences through its use of English and digital platforms such as YouTube and Facebook. In short, it highlights and utilizes the connections between the personal and the political, the private and the public, the offline and the online, and the local, national, and global as part of a process of 'becoming indigenous in the 21st century' (Clifford 2013).

Such contemporary Indigenous approaches have been inspired by new technologies and generational cultural changes, including attempts to break with some of the political connotations and limitations of established media and art practices. Ginsburg (1994:375) noted Aboriginal filmmakers in the early 1990s explored fiction and drama films to resist the risks of objectification and stereotyping associated with ethnographic documentary by outsiders. Today, young Aboriginals use phone cameras as creative alternatives to the tradition of dot painting. For some, 'the act of not painting is a highly political act' in response to socially and culturally stultifying forms of appropriating or commodifying this tradition (Miyarkka Media 2019:6). Based on research about the use of contemporary Information and Communication Technology (ICT) by Indigenous communities in Latin America, Pascal Lupien (2020:8) argues: 'ICTs allow Indigenous actors to perform, represent, debate, and re-conceptualize indigeneity in new and innovate ways. They provide tools for cultural positioning and survival, for countering essentialized understandings of indigeneity, as well as for new expressions of culture and identity.'

These media-related efforts at self-positioning, de-essentializing, and renewing cultural identity are shared by Ranu Welum. Together with other Indigenous activists in Indonesia and elsewhere, its members fulfil a role as cultural 'brokers', predominantly through their use of new art and media genres such as short documentary and popular social media trends. In this role, they function as the figureheads and drivers of activist movements; the translators of local and international languages, policies, and concepts; and the mediators between multiple individuals, social groups, institutions, and non-human actors (Bräuchler 2019:20–1). Based on the work of Sally Engle Merry (2006:40) and Johan Lindquist (2015a:872), Birgit Bräuchler (2019:21) argues that 'to be successful, brokers not only draw on existing cultural repertoires of the worlds between which they mediate, but they creatively adapt, manipulate and develop them further'. Such 'translators', in Merry's (2006:39) words, 'negotiate the middle in a field of power and opportunity', in which they have to demonstrate familiarity with the international discourses and practices as well as their

ability to adapt and adjust them to local circumstances and needs. Anna Tsing (2005:218) explains the historical roots of these translators and translations in Kalimantan and elsewhere in Indonesia:

The environmental movement of the 1980s and 1990s worked hard at translation. Globally influential texts were made available in Indonesian. Campaigns were publicized for the world in English as well as in Indonesian. Much work was also done translating within Indonesia, forming bridges across regional languages and across sectors of society. Problems of how to forge dialogues between elite and poor, majority and minority, and urban and rural were pressing; the question of translation stood at the center.

Lindquist (2015b:165) explains that the scale of such brokerage has become more complex due to the increased use of digital communication tools as well as the enhanced mobility of the brokers themselves. But it is precisely these extended, digital and in-person connectivities that have facilitated the alternative explorations and articulations of Dayak Indigeneity by media-savvy and cosmopolitan activists such as Emmanuela Shinta.

Apart from Ranu Welum, other examples of cultural, creative, and digital brokers in Indonesia are the leaders of environmental movements in Bali and the Aru Islands in the Moluccas, who have explored and redefined Indigeneity in and through creative media ranging from photography, film, blogs, and hashtags to posters, T-shirts, concerts, and street art (Bräuchler 2019:26–7). Edwin Jurriëns (2023b) has also demonstrated the use of similar media by so-called ‘artists’ in other parts of the archipelago, including Java and Sumatra, who have been key to the endurance and impact of local struggles for environmental sustainability and social justice. Similar to these other interconnections between art and activism, Ranu Welum demonstrates that creative symbolism and in-person activism are two sides of the same coin, which mutually need and strengthen each other. In the Balinese movement against land reclamation plans in Benoa Bay since 2013, the use of artistic imagery has facilitated the personalization of complex and abstract political issues; triggered people’s preparedness to come into action; and contributed to breaking with cultural stereotypes such as Balinese ‘peacefulness’ and the presumed reluctance to express political criticism or break the status quo (Jurriëns 2023b:126). Similarly, Ranu Welum’s creative production and in-person events firmly position the Dayak in the thick of critical environmental, political, and cultural action rather than a static field of past times and places.

6 Events, Media, and Bodies of Representation and Connectivity

Ranu Welum's most prominent cultural broker in Bräuchler's (2019) sense is its founder, Emmanuela Shinta,²⁴ a Dayak Maanyan filmmaker, author, and environmental activist who has written, directed, or produced the majority of the foundation's films. Shinta's BA in English Education (Shinta 2018:48), together with her creative and communicative talents, has been instrumental in the foundation's efforts at translating between local and foreign languages and concepts; mediating between national and international stakeholders; and giving publicity to its social and environmental campaigns.

Shinta's success in communicating the Dayak cause on a global level is demonstrated by her invited talks at numerous international forums, including the Ubud Writers and Readers Festival (2016, 2018), the Global Landscapes Forum (2019, 2023), TEDx (9 December 2020), and the Earthna summit (2023). She was appointed a member of the environmental meeting of the Advisory Board of the United Nations, called 'Stockholm 50+', which was held in Stockholm, 2–3 June 2022.²⁵ She has also been featured in the UNICEF Global White Paper 'Women health and climate' (2017), the *Asian Geographic* special issue 'Planet Under Fire' (number 117, issue 2, 2016), the PBS miniseries *The age of nature* (episode 3, 2020), and *The Guardian* podcast 'Indigenous activists on tackling the climate crisis: "We have done more than any government"' (4 November 2021), among others.²⁶ Shinta has shared her skills in cultural translation and mediation by providing online classes in public speaking, public relations, and creative writing,²⁷ and training more than 100 young Dayak people in filmmaking. These contributions to education and awareness creation are other examples of the concrete impact of Ranu Welum.

Shinta's own experiences of exploring and renewing Dayak identity are reflected in one of her self-published books, titled *Me, modernism and my indigenous roots* (Shinta 2018). This highly personal, diary-style book offers 'a perspective of an indigenous Dayak woman to life in the midst of environmental destruction and industrialization in her homeland, Kalimantan'.²⁸ It translates the experiences of herself and her community into a language, English, and popular and academic discourses around Indigeneity, modernism, industrialization, and environmental deterioration, that are shared and understood by an

24 <http://www.ranuwelum.org/our-story/> (accessed 5-8-2025).

25 <https://www.stockholm50.global/about/advisory-group> (accessed 5-8-2025).

26 <https://emmanuelashinta.org/notable-retrospective> (accessed 5-8-2025).

27 <https://emmanuelashinta.org/online-class> (accessed 5-8-2025).

28 <https://emmanuelashinta.org/books> (accessed 5-8-2025).

educated global audience. One prominent, and for some controversial, aspect of Shinta's Dayak identity, is her reconciliation of her Christian belief with her Indigeneity. In her book, she explains when and how she started to realize that this 'modernism' and her 'Indigenous roots' were not mutually exclusive, but complemented each other (Shinta 2018:122, 125):

To be honest, for the first seventeen years of my life, I was never proud to be a Dayak. Though I was offended by what some people said about Dayaks, deep in my heart I was ashamed of my own identity. [...] It took years for me to understand who I truly am. I am so passionate about God and I am never ashamed of it. I do realize what I say here will get different responses from those who are conservatives in their religion and beliefs. [...] It's interesting to say that religion is created by man while the understanding of divine supreme power is already owned by indigenous people. The understanding about God is already given to the indigenous from the very beginning. [...] I'm so proud of being an indigenous woman and so immersed in my relationship with God.

Her short environmental documentaries with and for Ranu Welum Media, which presents itself as 'The eyes of Dayaknese', include *When women fight, Part 1* (2016) and *Part 2* (2018); *Fight against the haze* (2016); *Sungai Kahayan dalam dilema* (*The Kahayan River in dilemma*, 2017); *Haze hacks* (2017); *Dayak: Facing the giants* (2019); *Through our lens* (2019); *Kaharapen* (2021); and *Ulin: The guardian* (2021). These documentaries signify key stages in the development of Ranu Welum's ideas and activism. They give attention to the role of women and youth; explore and express notions of Indigeneity; and analyse intersections between ecology, culture, and politics. They also represent and/or embody calls for action; achievements and challenges at the local and national levels; and efforts at creating international visibility and networking. Furthermore, they signal and promote a variety of creative approaches and production partnerships. In short, they document Ranu Welum's in-person activism and cultural diplomacy but also function as essential tools themselves in mediating between diverse groups and shaping ideas and actions around Indigeneity and environmentalism.

One of the most comprehensive insights into the development of Shinta's and Ranu Welum's verbal and visual discourses and networking strategies to address Indigenous rights and environmental destruction is offered by the documentary *Through our lens*, published on YouTube on 8 March 2021.²⁹ The doc-

29 <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=UnVKjvZPfKc> (accessed 5-8-2025).

umentary contains footage from previous documentaries but mainly focuses on Shinta's participation in the Global Landscapes Forum in Bonn, Germany, 22–23 June 2019. In her forum presentation, similar to the self-reflective and global perspectives in her books and other media productions, Shinta introduces herself in English as 'a woman from the Dayak Maanyan tribe'. Elsewhere in the video, she underlines the relevance of bringing the cause of the Dayak people to international gatherings:

I am always excited and grateful for the opportunity to connect with indigenous communities from other parts of the world [...] I am so grateful to be able to bring the voices of Dayak community in the forum like this, especially to build solidarity with other indigenous communities.

This not only concerns international Indigenous communities but also Indigenous representatives from elsewhere in Indonesia, with whom she rarely has the chance to meet in her home country. In the Bonn conference centre, she has an informal meeting with Father Anselmus Amo, an activist from West Papua. They met five years earlier during a visit to Patani in southern Thailand, where Shinta shot her first 'advocacy video'. Amo, who is preparing for his first international presentation in English, expresses his eagerness to learn from and with Shinta about the best ways to convey their messages, engage in debates, and build partnerships in such forums. This encounter shows that international conventions not only bring Indonesian *adat* communities and their concerns to the global stage but also facilitate connectivity and the sharing of cultural brokering and media strategies between communities from Indonesia itself.

At the start of the documentary, Shinta expresses her personal belief that 'even the lowest voice can be heard over all intimidation when it is telling the truth'. But the film also gives great insight into how her media savviness and strategic use of bodily presence and self-imaging derived from contemporary social media and selfie culture, enables her to connect with international representatives, youth communities, and online audiences. In one of the documentary segments, aptly captioned 'Shinta's self camera', Shinta films herself wandering around the conference centre, or talking and arranging her outfit and make-up in her hotel room. In one of the scenes, she reflects on the importance of this self-imaging in making the Dayak cause visible to the world: 'maybe people will easily recognise me if I come up with the same clothes every time'. In her book *Me, modernism and my indigenous roots*, Shinta (2018:21) further complicates such politics of visual appearance:

I like to guess what is on people's minds whenever they see me dressed in a traditional outfit or ripped-up jeans and a T-shirt. Even when it comes to a traditional costume, it is not so traditional nowadays. Some people like to see something unusual, something they can never find in a shopping mall. However, I am never happy with the idea that an indigenous person must wear attire from a thousand years ago just to show his or her identity. Why do we have to present a personal [*sic*] of our tribal identity? Is it so outside people can identify us easily?

It is statements like this, and Shinta's highly varied repertoire of self-representations, that illustrate the tensions, complementary values, and ultimately open-ended nature of the intersections between individuality and communality in contemporary constructions and mediations of Indigeneity. They also point to the gendered dimensions of her and Ranu Welum's cultural brokering, complementing other unique dimensions of their Indigenous identity-making, such as youth and religion. This complexity confirms the findings of other studies seeking to disassociate youthful selfie and other social media culture from stereotypical connotations of narcissism and slacktivism (Halimatusa'diyah 2024).

7 *When Women Fight: Gendering the Indigenous and Environmental Struggles*

With her central role in the production and content of Ranu Welum's films, Shinta has added her own gendered contribution to Indonesian film production and content. In the first decades after Indonesia's independence in 1945, the role of women in the film industry was mainly limited to acting, with only a few women working as film directors (Kurnia 2013:33–4). During the New Order, films tended to follow the state ideology by representing women in their ideal roles as wives and mothers (Sen 1994). In the late 1980s, the film industry suffered a life-threatening 'crisis' from the political repression and the competition of commercial television, international cinema, and video imports (Nugroho and Herlina 2015:186–227; Kurnia 2013:33). The democratic reform or Reformasi of the late 1990s and the enhanced access to digital technology inspired an Indonesian film revival, with dozens of female directors and producers at its forefront (Hughes-Freeland 2011:423–4; Kurnia 2013:35; Michalik 2015:379–80).

The increased female participation has translated in film content focusing on women and female perspectives; women directors winning prestigious

domestic film awards; festivals exclusively focusing on films created by women; and women filmmakers participating in various forms of activism, with some of them openly identifying as feminist or queer (Kurnia 2013:33–6; Michalik 2015:380–5; Paramaditha 2007). In the early Reformasi period, female directors, and producers such as Ariani Djalal (year of birth unknown), Lulu Ratna (b. 1972), Shanti Harmayn (b. 1967), Yuli Andari Merdikaningtyas (b. 1980), and Ucu Agustin (b. 1976) contributed to a renaissance in documentary-making in Indonesia (Hughes-Freeland 2011:432–8). A recent example, apart from Shinta's work, is *Tanah ibu kami* (*Our mothers' land*), a documentary focusing on female environmental activists from different corners of the archipelago, written and produced by investigative journalist Febriana Firdaus (b. 1983) (Jurriëns 2023a).

Similar to the post-New Order female film production discussed by Hughes-Freeland, Shinta's work offers a form of creativity that 'will become more than an ephemeral act of solipsism or a "one-off", and will instead "stick" in the socio-cultural sphere and contribute to an ongoing creative process' (Hughes-Freeland 2011:418). With Yuli Andari Merdikaningtyas, she shares an interest in documentary-making, local culture, and environmental issues. However, while Merdikaningtyas presents research-based ethnographic documentaries, predominantly about Sumbawa (Hughes-Freeland 2011:436), Shinta provides highly personalized, activist statements based on lived experiences in Central Kalimantan. Similar to Firdaus, Shinta is explicit about giving 'women's perspectives' (Kurnia 2013:37), by highlighting the existence and importance of Indigenous women's agency and leadership in environmental affairs. Shinta strongly engages with the selfie culture of speaking directly to the camera/audience, while Firdaus's style can be described as a form of Trinh T. Minh-ha's 'speaking nearby' (Chen 1992), in which the filmmaker's interaction with her female conversation partners is the focus point (Jurriëns 2023a).

Shinta's gendered and activist approach to Indigeneity, filmmaking, and cultural brokerage is reflected in her two-film documentary series *When women fight* (Part 1 and Part 2). This series covers the start of Ranu Welum's activism by focusing on the actions and perspectives of Shinta and other female leaders of the foundation's environmental and health campaigns, including Roro Ardy Garini and Lina Karolin. Their presence, activities, and statements in the films make the complex issues relatable to young, international, and female audiences by intersecting the personal and the political, the private and the public, the individual and the communal, and the online and the offline.

On YouTube, Ranu Welum describes Part 1 (2016) of the documentary as 'a story of people struggling during the worst toxic haze in 2015 and their hope

being told by a young Dayak activist [Shinta] based in Palangka Raya, Central Kalimantan.³⁰ The film represents the context and start of the Youth Act Kalimantan, Ranu Welum's inaugural programme for practical forms of activism. It was published on the digital platform on 2 May 2016 (amassing 1,191 views by December 2023) and was also screened at various festivals and conferences in 2016, including the Freedom Film Festival in Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia, the ASEAN People's Forum in Dili, Timor Leste, and the Ubud Writers and Readers Festival in Ubud, Bali.

The documentary starts with footage of Shinta leading a street demonstration in front of the office of the governor of Central Kalimantan in Palangka Raya during the 2015 haze. With a megaphone, she expresses people's fear and frustration and calls for politicians to take responsibility and act. In different sections of the documentary, she has a strong bodily presence, and she is seen wearing headphones and talking straight to the camera against a background of rice fields, as if intersecting the online and offline worlds. She contextualizes and politicizes the haze with her personal experiences and the broader social and historical background.

With a strong sense of understatement, she expresses 'a little bit of a trauma' from breathing in toxic air from the massive, recurring peatland fires since 1997, when she was only five years old. During the 2015 haze, she 'felt hopeless, only waiting for the arrival of more dead people'. The documentary explains that the street demonstrations led by Shinta were to no avail. The aid from the national government to the region was limited, even in comparison with the military support and provision of masks and oxygen safe houses in Riau, Sumatra, another province struggling with the haze. Public attention only started to increase with the media coverage of Singapore-based television station Channel NewsAsia (CNA) and the provision of N95 masks by international donor organizations.

Similar to some of the other female protagonists in the documentary, Shinta conveys information with a voice and facial expression that combine a spirit of activism with feelings of anger, sadness, and exhaustion. Her words and appearance show that her political activism is rooted in lived experiences and is both individual and communal in nature. This is also reflected in Lina Karolin's emotional account of her personal experiences as a volunteer. These experiences range from receiving the gratitude of parents for the donation of masks, to the challenges of reaching remote locations, supporting ill children, and fighting physical and mental fatigue.

30 <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=wPgQG1vTPbg> (accessed 5-8-2025).

Against the background of the 2015 fires, Ranu Welum launched its Youth Act Kalimantan campaign to recruit youth for firefighting and healthcare activities. In the documentary, Shinta interconnects lived experiences, verbal and visual discourses, and activism by explaining that this Youth Act is a beautiful idea (*ide*) that also involves real action (*tindakan nyata*):

2015 has passed, what about this year? We don't want to see the fire again, we don't want to experience the haze again. We want people to care and get involved in ending the fires and haze. We launch a campaign called Youth Act.

The documentary demonstrates the leading role of women in this campaign by presenting the work of Roro Ardya Garini, current Ranu Welum executive director and former coordinator (2016–2018) of the Youth Act Kalimantan. Garini elaborates on the communal activist aims of the initiative: 'fighting for people who have been robbed of their rights, uniting young people in Palangka Raya in fighting the forest fires and haze that have been recurring for 18 years in a row'. In her statements, she also interconnects Dayak culture and environmentalism. While acknowledging that Indonesia is one of the greatest contributors to global greenhouse gases because of deforestation in Kalimantan, she believes Indigenous people have the wisdom and skills to contribute to reforestation and the restoration of ecosystems.

In the documentary, Shinta and her fellow women activists encourage the minister of environment and forestry to visit the region and witness people's health risks in person. Their statements are backed with expert comments, the footage of polluted skies and water, and the poor health conditions of people, particularly children, mothers, and the elderly, in local neighbourhoods and hospitals. Backed by more than 50 other women who had joined the movement by 2016, Shinta vows at the end of the documentary: 'We will never stop [the fight] (*Kita tidak akan pernah berhenti*):'

When women fight, Part 2 (2018), published on YouTube on 17 August 2019,³¹ also genders and politicizes the struggles for environmental and social justice by presenting women's bodies and experiences. Some of the most impressive images in the documentary show Shinta in the thick of things, at the border between the Taruna and Tumbang Nusa villages in the Pulang Pisau regency in Central Kalimantan, August 2018. She is seen sweating and having difficulties breathing while wearing an oxygen mask. In the back-

31 <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=AtVc23knIZY&t=2s> (accessed 5-8-2025).

ground, the yellow and red flames of wild peatland fires contrast with the pitch-black night. Shinta, with her face to the camera, explains the peat is deep and the fire is spreading fast, while the volunteer firefighters have only limited access to the lands and are forced to continue working through the night.

The film focuses on the early activities and achievements of the Youth Act Kalimantan programme, including environmental awareness-raising events and public criticism of the (lack of) government action and policies. It has footage of the provision of free medical services in villages (2015), firefighting training for youth (2016), educational sessions at schools (2016), a fundraising event for the free distribution of milk to children (2016), and efforts at making the problems in Kalimantan known to the world in international meetings such as the Global Issues Network (GIN) conference (2016) and the Global Landscape Forum (2017). It also has interviews with representatives of UNICEF and the Singapore-based Big Red Button, which both assisted Ranu Welum with the creation of haze shelters. In a video message recorded from a moving car, symbolizing her mobility, energy, and busy agenda, Shinta refers to the necessity of her foundation's increasingly international orientation: 'Our voices are not sufficiently listened to, policy makers never involve the voice of the locals, let us talk about these issues in international forums then.'

In another part of the documentary, Karolin and several Dayak farmers express their concerns directly to Siti Nurbaya Bakar, the minister of environment and forestry (2014–2024), who paid a visit to Central Kalimantan in 2016. While watching a recording of the visit on her laptop, Shinta criticizes the minister for her condescending attitude and oblique answers, including her statement that 'all health problems will be solved later'. Facing the camera, she questions the government's inaction and wonders how much longer the people of Kalimantan need to wait, after having already experienced the haze for close to two decades at the time of the ministerial visit. Such explicit political criticism and calls for government accountability are rarely found in the coverage of social and environmental topics in the Indonesian mainstream print and broadcast media.

8 Intersecting the Personal, Communal, and Natural

When women fight, Part 2, highlights the individual bodies, voices, experiences, concerns, and actions of young female activists not in isolation but in broader socio-political contexts, and in dialogue with the voices of local farmers and other members and leaders of Indigenous communities. It pays special

attention to Indonesian legislation, such as paragraph 50 of the 1999 Undang-Undang No. 41 tentang Kehutanan (Law No. 41 on Forestry), which by prohibiting the use of traditional burning techniques for clearing land for farming has led to the criminalization and arrests of local farmers. It presents the stories of farmers who had lost their rubber plantations to the fires or were forced to stop farming altogether.

In one of the documentary segments, Shinta walks through the village with a local farmer called Ukaiman, who states that ‘the government solution [the 1999 Law No. 41 on Forestry] is actually another way of killing Dayak people’ due to the lack of employment opportunities outside farming. The farmer was arrested after a conflict with a palm oil company that had taken away his 20 hectares of land. He shows Shinta photographs of men, allegedly policemen in civilian clothes, behaving ‘like thugs’. He mentions that he has given up on waiting for the outcome of a lawsuit he had filed against the palm oil company, due to a lack of progress and financial and mental exhaustion. Nevertheless, he would support young people willing to take up the challenge and continue the fight. Elsewhere in the documentary, a Dayak leader called Sensus explains that his ancestors burnt lands to make it suitable for planting rice for hundreds of years without causing any haze.

On stage at an international convention, Shinta also shares the story of an elderly farmer who was unaware of the ban on agricultural burning. Out of despair after being fined, he committed suicide. Shinta adds that, in contrast, big palm oil, logging, and mining companies have continued to grab and destroy forests and lands without legal or financial consequences. She argues that the source of the problems are not the forest fires and haze as such, but forms of ‘modern colonization’ (*kolonisasi modern*). Also here, she expresses socio-political criticism and interconnects the individual and the communal through a public, bodily presence; personalized storytelling and visual appearance; and educated, international discourse.

Towards the end of the documentary, various verbal, textual, and visual statements known from youth and social media culture are made in explicit support of the cause of the Dayak people. They are similar to the media and imagery used in the national ‘Melawan Asap’ (Fighting the Haze) street demonstrations and social and mainstream media campaigns at one of the worst peaks of the haze disaster in Sumatra and Kalimantan in 2015 (Jurriëns 2023b:141–8). Still images show Shinta holding banners with the texts ‘Dayak— # the guardians of the forest’ and ‘Will you stand with me’, respectively. The last image, in front of the Golden Gate Bridge in San Francisco, confirms her mobility and personalized, hashtag-style cultural brokerage. The documentary concludes with a black screen and a female voice-over underlining Ranu

Welum's political stand on the intersections between environmental destruction and Indigenous identity and rights:

Building infrastructure, industrialization, agrarian and natural resources management, are they made to benefit Dayak communities? Or just a camouflage to fulfill personal ambitions of those who call themselves leaders of the country? Forests are cut down, rivers are polluted, land is grabbed, our people oppressed, displaced, jailed, but we haven't given up, we will continue to speak up. This is our fight, and we will never stop [...] This film is dedicated to indigenous people's rights defenders in Indonesia and all over the world who fight the same fight with us, the Dayaks.

The foundation's evolving international partnerships and growing reputation are illustrated by a more recent documentary, *Ulin: The guardian*, published on YouTube on 20 December 2021.³² The documentary, arguably the film with the highest image and production quality by Ranu Welum Media to date, was directed by Shinta and created with support of the Asia Indigenous Peoples Pact, UNESCO, and Youth in Landscapes Initiative. The script was written by one of Ranu Welum's Youth Act Kalimantan coordinators, Sumarni Laman. While the earlier documentaries provided strong activist statements and broad socio-political contexts, perhaps necessary to make the foundation's mission and vision known to the world, this film provides a specific example of the bond between the natural environment and Dayak culture and wisdom. It gives agency to nature itself by presenting a detailed and intimate account of a tree, and the daily, ongoing activities involved in its conservation.

The documentary focuses on *ulin* or ironwood, an extremely sturdy tree with a high ecological, cultural, and economic value. It can grow in clay and sandy soils, and is resistant to termites, floods, and temperature changes. As reflected in the title, some Dayak groups consider *ulin*, or *tawudi'en* in the local language, a spiritual guardian (*pelindung spiritual*) that protects the customary territory from beasts and evil spirits. The documentary explains that *ulin* is under threat by loggers, who can earn as much as Rp 40 million (US\$ 2,500) per felled tree on the black market. The documentary contains a social media video of an illegal logger boastfully felling a 100-year-old tree. It also refers to other threats, including the removal of the *ulin* tree from the list of protected flora and fauna in the 2018 revised Peraturan Menteri Lingkungan Hidup dan Kehutanan (Ministry of Environment and Forest Regulation) No. 106.

32 <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=3iFBngfBAV4> (accessed 5-8-2025).

A key protagonist in the film, apart from *ulin*, is the ironwood conservationist Peresto from the village of Talekoi. The documentary shows Peresto providing training in collecting seeds and nursing seedlings to a group of Ranu Welum's Kalimantan Green Warriors. Together with the locals, the volunteers have started an *ulin* conservation area, which relies on the seeds of the oldest, 200-year-old *ulin* tree in Talekoi. The documentary ends with a drone shot of the Kalimantan Green Warriors, standing in a circle with pots of seedlings in their hands, as a symbol of their efforts to restore nature. Providing these images of intimacy with, and care for, nature functions as another discursive strategy by Ranu Welum to interconnect the individual, communal, and natural; generate awareness about, and empathy for, the Dayak people among local and international audiences; and trigger support for the social and environmental struggles of Indigenous peoples in Kalimantan and elsewhere.

9 Conclusion

Ranu Welum has emerged as a specific articulation of Dayak Indigenous identity by young, media-savvy people at the juncture of various, often mutually opposing, forces in contemporary Indonesia, including new media technology and freedom of expression on the one hand and the infringement of people's basic rights by government and business on the other. Similar to other *adat* communities, the foundation addresses local histories, land rights, and legal structures. At the same time, it places identity, language, and cultural expression and representation at the heart of the environmental and social struggles of Indigenous people in Central Kalimantan. It approaches culture and identity not as fixed in tradition and history, but as dynamic processes that can be shaped and changed in accordance with personal experiences and communal needs. One of its key missions is to make the Dayak cause known to the international world, as it realizes that the environmental and social issues cannot be solved on a local or national level only. It particularly seeks to connect and share experiences with other Indigenous communities in Indonesia and worldwide.

Ranu Welum is steered by predominantly female activists and media producers, who try to trigger social and environmental awareness, action, and renewal by combining informational and creative media such as documentaries, blogs, and tweets with on-site educational, firefighting, and land and forest restoration programmes. These activist-producers function as cultural brokers between online and offline activities, local and international languages and discourses, contemporary media and traditional knowledge, and younger and older generations, among others. They discuss communal needs and concerns

by using the self-imaging and other individualized, in-situ visual approaches known from the social and mobile media used by young people. Emmanuela Shinta and her fellow female activists have a strong visual presence and personal storytelling style in Ranu Welum's documentaries. They connect the lived experiences of individuals that especially young audiences can relate to, with the broader historical and political contexts of the social and environmental issues. For these Indigenous media producers, the communal and the individual are both political; they do not necessarily exclude but can, in fact, reinforce each other.

With her books and media productions and appearances at international conferences and conventions, Shinta puts the body, thoughts, and words of a young woman centre stage at the definition of contemporary Dayak Indigeneity. Through real-life or virtual connections with other prominent female and male activists, she connects Dayak activism with the struggle for Indigenous rights and social and environmental justice worldwide. As demonstrated by documentaries such as *When women fight* (Part 1 and Part 2), and practical initiatives such as the Youth Act Kalimantan, the activists bring a new, youthful, and gendered energy and style to this ongoing struggle. Despite enduring a heavy physical and mental toll, these Dayak activists are committed to learn from, and with, others and continue the fight. While Ranu Welum's impact can be felt in creating public and international awareness about the Dayak plight, providing media training and environmental education to local youth, and assisting with firefighting and forest conservation and restoration efforts, the foundation is unavoidably confronted with the never-ending challenge of resisting and negotiating the much-larger national and international corporate and government interests of natural resource exploitation in Kalimantan.

Similar to other environmental movements in Indonesia, such as the Balinese anti-reclamation movement since 2013 and the broader anti-haze protests in Sumatra and Kalimantan since 2015, Ranu Welum combines art and activism to sustain its social and environmental campaigns. It also shares with a post-New Order generation of female documentary makers the use of gendered approaches to politics and nature. It stands out, however, for its efforts to continuously personalize and make relatable the—often very complex and abstract—political and environmental issues, and to rethink and reshape notions of Indigeneity, through the activist, community-oriented use of selfie and other social-media inspired creativity. This article urges analysis of the activist potential of this broader repertoire of media and genres, and for moving the research around Indigeneity and its articulations beyond the arbitrary boundaries between the individual and the communal, the traditional and the contemporary, and the local and the global.

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